

A Study on Awareness about Swayam among Teachers and Students: A Government of India Initiative on Online Learning

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Abstract

Evolution of technology has impact on education, on line education that takes place over the internet provides a platform to learn over internet, MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) popularized online education. As a result of that, SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-learning for Young Aspiring Minds) programme was initiated by Government of India. The objective of the programme is to take the best teaching learning resources to all with no costs. To enquire the awareness among teachers and students about SWAYAM and the reputation of SWAYAM, an online survey has been conducted among teachers and students by using social media platforms.

The results show that there is need for promotion of SWAYAM among the students at the undergraduate level. The conclusion suggests more awareness is required.

Keywords: MOOCs, SWAYAM, Online Education.

Introduction

In India, MOOCs was first started by IIT Bombay, Mumbai. The research study reveals that students from India being the second largest in terms of enrolment in MOOCs after US. Students from India have shown lots of interest looking forward to utilize the platform of MOOCs. As a result July 9, 2017 SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-learning for Young Aspiring Minds) programme was initiated by Government of India. It is designed to achieve the three cardinal principles of education policy namely access, equity and quality. The objective of this effort is to take the best teaching learning resources to all including the most disadvantaged to the knowledge economy. SWAYAM platform is developed by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) with the help of Microsoft. Currently, it is in developing stage covering various courses include school, certificate, diploma, under-graduate, post-graduate courses. In future, they're going to introduce engineering, law and other professional courses.

Till 2018 more than 39 Lakhs learners have enrolled in more than 1600+ MOOCs courses that have been run through SWAYAM.

60,000 persons have completed the courses. It is the endeavor of MHRD to align the courses on the SWAYAM portal with the curriculum of Universities.

Back Ground

SWAYAM is a web based learning platform. It covers numerous coverage from school level to post graduate level. The SWAYAM platform is specifically designed to benefit students from remote/backward area, working professionals, college dropouts. Government of India started SWAYAM for the benefit of students/researcher/faculties. It is growing day by day as UGC started credit programme through SWAYAM. Its courses cover four quadrants like e-content, e-tutorial, web resources, and self- assessment. Presently seven hundred and fifty four programs have been initiated. Out of which forty five programs under school category, fifteen certificate programs, twenty nine diploma programs, three hundred and eighty six undergraduate programs and two seventy nine post graduate programs are in progress. SWAYAM will provide great opportunity to Indian students to learn without fearing from failure.

Four Quadrant Approach Cycle in SWAYAM

Literature Review

- According to Anuva Samanta (2018) SWAYAM is a MOOCs compatible open and distance education environment which is available through the Information and Communication Technology (ICT). This study explores how this new mode of education can bring opportunities to learners from all section of society to participate in the education set up.
- According to BIJU NARZARY (2017 – 2019) study found that among the four MOOC initiatives of India identified, the NPTEL is the oldest one as it was established in 2003. SWAYAM which was established in 2017 is the latest one. All platforms except Inffibnet Vidya-Mitra have provision for integrating credits earned into their regular programmes being pursued.
- According to Bharti (2014), “SWAYAM is a platform for new India where quality education is affordable and self-learning is fruitful not only for enrolled but also for professionals and dropouts. With quality content, best online lectures, great discussions, knowledgeable assessment quizzes, SWAYAM will provide great opportunity to Indian students to learn without fearing from failure.”

So, from here we can predict that SWAYAM has a great future indeed. Now what is the view point of teachers and students about SWAYAM? How much it will benefit us? What are the areas to be developed? So, from the view point of a teachers and students a study is required to find the solution of above mentioned questions.

Objective of the Study

- To know the awareness about SWAYAM among teachers and students.
- To find out the popularity of SWAYAM
- To know which teaching process is most interesting in SWAYAM
- Recommendations for improvement of SWAYAM.

Methodology

An online survey was conducted among teachers and students about the awareness of SWAYAM following a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was made using Google Form. The questionnaire link was distributed through social networking sites and platforms like different teachers and students groups via WhatsApp, and LinkedIn etc.). The social media platform has been selected because teachers and students are mostly connected with social media each other. So, it is expected to get more response in least time. As a whole, total 102 responses were received and most of them are students.

Limitations of the Study

Due to lack of time only online survey methods have been used. All the respondents have not responded all the answers correctly. Though the online questionnaire was distributed among so many group of professionals and students, but received very few number of responses

Results and Analysis

Gender

The online survey questionnaire was distributed among teachers and students in the field of commerce and management majority of the respondents are Male (64.8%) and the female respondents are (39.22%).

Table 1 Gender of the respondents

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	62	60.78
Female	40	39.22
Total	102	100

Profile

The results reveals that most of the respondents are students (64.70%) and Teachers are (35.30%).

Table 2 Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Number of respondents	Percentage
Student	66	64.70
Teachers	36	35.30
Total	102	100

Minimum Qualification

It is seen that the minimum qualifications of the respondent teachers have Master’s Degree (35.30%) in commerce or management and some have also higher degree like MPhil (27.77%), and PhD (16.67%). So, it is clear that the respondent teachers are well educated.

Do You Know about MOOCs (Massive open online courses)

The result shows that (31%) of the respondents are aware of MOOCs and the majority (69%) of the respondents are not aware about MOOCs.

Have You Heard about SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-learning for Young Aspiring Minds)?

This study shows that (30%) have heard about SWAYAM and the majority of the respondents are not aware about SWAYAM. This indicates promotion of SWAYAM is required to create awareness among respondents.

Have You Registered for Any Courses in SWAYAM?

It is observed that 90% of the respondents are not registered any courses in SWAYAM. This reveals SWAYAM authority can give proposal to make an option to include choice in semester credit system in courses running in universities.

Which Teaching Process is Most Interesting in SWAYAM?

There are four types of teaching process is used in SWAYAM. But most (37.25%) the respondents prefers video lectures and (21.56%) of the respondents prefers self-assessment and customized reading material followed by online discussion forum for clearing doubts (19.63%).

Table 3 Most Interesting Teaching Process in SWAYAM

Teaching Process	Number	Percentage
Video Lectures	38	37.25
Self-Assessments	22	21.56
Customized reading material that can be downloaded or printed	22	21.56
An online discussion forum for clearing doubts	20	19.63
Total	102	100

Recommendations for improvement of SWAYAM

There are so many recommendations received from the respondents for improvement of SWAYAM. Major points have been listed here.

- Users and subject expert’s participation can make it more reliable.
- It is good platform to learn and gain knowledge. Government should advertise on media like Radio and TV channels.
- SWAYAM authority can give proposal to make an option to include choice in semester credit system in courses running in universities.
- Need more details regarding this in all institutions to create awareness among students.

Conclusions

This study gives an idea and information about awareness of SWAYAM among teachers and students. MOOCs has multiple advantages, keeping the fact in mind Government of India started SWAYAM for the benefit of students/researcher/faculties. SWAYAM will provide great opportunity to Indian students to learn without fearing from failure. The results of this study reveal

that promotion of SWAYAM among students and teachers is required. The paper concludes that more awareness is required and more courses should be added time to time. Some more interactive and innovative teaching techniques should be introduced. Government should promote SWAYAM through advertisements on media like Radio and TV channels, social networking sites and other platforms. SWAYAM will have a grand success in near future

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